

1 Water distribution and ionic balance in response to high CO₂ treatments in wild
2 strawberries (*Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois)

3

4 María Blanch, María T. Sanchez-Ballesta, María I. Escribano, Carmen Merodio*

5

6 Department of Characterization, Quality and Security, Institute of Food Science
7 Technology and Nutrition (ICTAN-CSIC), Jose Antonio Novais 10, Madrid 28040,
8 Spain.

9 *Corresponding author: Carmen Merodio, Department of Characterization, Quality and
10 Security, ICTAN-CSIC, Jose Antonio Novais 10, Madrid 28040, Spain.

11 Tel: +34 91 5492300

12 Fax: + 34 91 5493627

13 E-mail adress: merodio@ictan.csic.es

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22 **Abstract**

23 An important beneficial effect of short-term treatment with 20% CO₂ is the maintenance
24 of water status at levels similar to those found in freshly harvested strawberries. We
25 investigated the effect of CO₂ treatment (20% or 40% CO₂ for 3 days) on intercellular
26 water loss prevention, and on the accumulation of organic and inorganic solutes in wild
27 strawberries stored at 0 °C (*Fragaria x vesca* L., cv. Mara de Bois). In addition to
28 mediating osmotic adjustment, treatment with 20% CO₂ had protective effect on cellular
29 structure, maintaining ion homeostasis and preventing the movement of water into the
30 intercellular spaces. By contrast, in both untreated fruit and when strawberries were
31 treated with 40% CO₂ the intercellular spaces were filled with aqueous solution, as
32 visualized by LT-SEM. Furthermore, 20% CO₂ treatment controlled weight loss and
33 maintained the K⁺/Na⁺ homeostasis similar to that found in freshly harvested fruit,
34 preventing the imbalance of K⁺ and Na⁺ observed in both untreated and 40% CO₂-
35 treated fruit.

36

37 **Keywords:** strawberry; microstructure; high CO₂; organic acids; free amino acids; ionic
38 content; water status.

39

40

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Given the economic value of their fruit, particularly due to its flavor and taste, several
44 cultivars of wild *Fragaria x vesca* L. that undergo repeat flowering are of special
45 interest. The recently sequenced genome of *Fragaria x vesca* L. is the smallest known
46 plant genome, with the exception of *Arabidopsis*. However, the fruit of strawberries are
47 highly perishable, and they are sensitive to water loss and fungal decay. Exposure to
48 CO₂-enriched atmosphere is a common postharvest technique to control fungal decay in
49 varieties of cultivated and wild strawberries (Ke et al., 1991; Almenar et al., 2006).
50 Indeed, concentrations of 15-20% CO₂ are routinely used for prolonged period of times to
51 control decay with no detrimental effects on soluble solid content, titratable acidity or
52 consumer acceptance. However, to obtain the maximum benefit of high concentration
53 CO₂ treatment it is necessary to carefully select the concentration, temperature and
54 treatment duration for the specific variety of strawberry. Despite decades of applying
55 this technology, the mechanisms underlying CO₂ tolerance and CO₂-induced damage
56 remain poorly understand. Thus, it is necessary to distinguish between the metabolic
57 responses associated with damage and those that are in fact adaptive, favoring storage at
58 low temperature.

59 The responses of tolerant fruit to high concentrations of CO₂ involve many complex
60 pathways. Characterization of the roles of specific metabolites in these complex networks
61 may provide insight into the basic mechanism of tolerance to high CO₂ and to a range of
62 other environmental factors. Among the specific metabolites studied, γ -aminobutyric acid
63 (GABA) accumulates in CO₂-treated fruit of all cultivars of *Fragaria x ananassa*
64 described (Deewatthanawong et al., 2010). In cherimoya, significant increases in GABA
65 levels were also detected after 3 days of exposure to high concentrations of CO₂, an effect
66 that was reversed by transfer to air (Merodio et al., 1998). The accumulation of GABA

67 (Kinnersley and Turano, 2000; Bouche and Fromm, 2004) plays several important roles,
68 including the regulation of cytoplasmic pH, which varies in fruit treated with high
69 concentrations of CO₂ (Lange and Kader, 1997). Also, alterations in the homeostasis of
70 the intracellular pH in response to different environmental stress have been reported in
71 some plant species (Yoshida, 1994, Muñoz et al., 2001). Preventing cytoplasmic
72 acidosis in stressful conditions may also involve malate and succinate metabolism,
73 (Roberts et al., 1992; Menegus et al., 1989), and changes in the levels of malate and
74 succinic acid in CO₂-treated fruit are also well documented (Maldonado et al., 2004;
75 Fernandez-Trujillo et al., 1999; Ponce-Valadez and Watkins, 2008). Accumulation of
76 non-structural carbohydrates such as fructooligosaccharides (FOS) has also been
77 observed in grapes in response to short-term exposure to CO₂ (Blanch et al., 2011).
78 Fructose-based polymers have been increasingly recognized as protective agents against
79 abiotic stresses in plants (Valluru and Van den Ende, 2008) and they might serve a role
80 as macromolecular structures protectors.

81 Water status is a prominent parameter to monitor plant damage caused by environmental
82 stressful conditions (Vertucci and Stushnuff, 1992; Hitmi et al., 2000). Short-term
83 treatment with 20% CO₂ prevents perturbations in the water fractions and the water
84 leakage during low temperature storage (Goñi et al., 2011). We propose that
85 modifications in the water status in response to high CO₂ concentrations and low
86 temperature may be due to changes in the protection of cellular structures and in the
87 accumulation of metabolites with osmolyte function and water binding capacity. Thus,
88 the main objective of the present study was to analyze all the major osmotically relevant
89 solutes, both inorganic (cations and anions) and organic (amino acids, organic acids and
90 soluble sugars) in wild strawberries cv. Mara de Bois untreated and treated with 20% or
91 40% CO₂. In addition, we set out to compare the volume and distribution of aqueous

92 solution in intercellular spaces in untreated, CO₂-treated and freshly harvested
93 strawberries. In this way, we hoped to gain insight into the protective mechanisms
94 activated by beneficial CO₂-treatment during storage.

95

96 **2. Materials and Methods**

97 **2.1. Plant material**

98 Organic strawberries (*Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois) were harvested by hand on 17
99 May 2010 at the first flowering at the Monjarama orchard in San Sebastian de los Reyes
100 (Madrid, Spain). After harvest, fruit were transported to Institute of Food Science
101 Technology and Nutrition within 2 h. Fruit selected for uniform size and colour were
102 stored at 0 °C (\pm 0.5) and >95% relative humidity in three sealed containers with a
103 capacity of 1 m³. Ten plastic boxes containing approximately 1 kg of strawberries per
104 box were stored in each container for 3 days and exposed to a continuous flow of air
105 (untreated fruit) or a gas mixture containing 20% or 40% CO₂. The same O₂
106 concentration (20%) was maintained in all three lots. Carbon dioxide and oxygen
107 concentrations were measured using a gas analyzer PBI Dansensor mod. Checkmate
108 9900. Before and after treatment (3 days), 45 strawberries from five boxes were
109 removed at random from each of the treatment groups, frozen in liquid nitrogen and
110 stored at -80 °C for further analysis.

111 **2.2. Extraction and chromatographic determination of the total soluble sugars and** 112 **organic acids**

113 To determine the total soluble sugar (glucose, fructose and sucrose) and organic acid
114 (oxalic, citric, succinic and malic acids) concentrations, 3 g of each sample was
115 homogenized in 10 mL of ultra-pure water, centrifuged at 30,000 x g for 20 min, and

116 the supernatants were then filtered through a membrane of 0.45 μm pore size. Sugar
117 determination was carried out by HPAEC-PAD with a Metrosep Carb 1-250 IC column
118 (4.6 x 250 mm), as described elsewhere (Bodelón et al., 2010). Organic acids were
119 analyzed by HPAEC using a Metrohm Advanced Compac ion chromatography
120 instrument (867 IC. Metrohm) equipped with a Metrosep Organic Acids column (7.8 x
121 100 mm), an IC-819 conductivity detector, an IC Pump 818 and an IC-837
122 degasser.coupled. Samples were eluted from the column with an isocratic gradient of
123 0.5 mM HClO_4 with 50 mM LiCl suppression over 20 min at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min.
124 Data was acquired with the ICNet 2.3 Metrohm software.

125 Oxalic, citric, succinic and malic acids were identified by their retention times and
126 quantified on the basis of calibration curves derived from standards. The content of each
127 sugar and organic acid was expressed as mg/g fresh weight (FW) of the sample, and the
128 data represents the means of the three replicates, two different measurements being
129 made.

130 **2.3. Extraction and determination of free amino acids**

131 A fruit sample (1 g) was homogenized in 2.5 mL of ultra-pure water containing 5 mM
132 chloridric acid and maintained at 4 °C overnight. Samples were centrifuged at 30,000 x
133 g for 20 min, after which the supernatants were filtered through a membrane of 0.45 μm
134 pore size, and an aliquot of each sample was injected into an Amino Acid Analyzer
135 (Pharmacia, Biochrom 20). Profile analyses of free amino acids in untreated and CO_2 -
136 treated strawberries includes also those of proline and the ubiquitous non-protein amino
137 acid GABA. Free amino acids were identified by comparing the retention times of
138 standard mixtures and the amino acid content, expressed as $\mu\text{mol/g}$ FW of the sample.

139 **2.4. Ion analysis**

140 A fruit sample (1 g) was homogenized for 5 minutes in 10 mL of ultra-pure water (for
141 Na^+ and K^+) or 10 mL of ultra-pure water slightly acidified with 5 mM chloridric acid
142 (for Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) and analyzed as described previously (Cataldi et al., 2003).
143 Samples were centrifuged at 2,000 x g for 20 min, after which the levels of soluble ions
144 were determined in the supernatants. Atomic emission spectrometry was used to
145 determine K^+ , using a 5100PC atomic absorption spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer, Norwalk,
146 CT, USA) with an air-acetylene flame. Levels of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Na^+ were determined
147 by atomic absorption spectrometry with the same instrument, using a multi-element
148 (Ca-Mg-Zn) hollow-cathode lamp.

149 **2.5. Water distribution and microstructural analysis**

150 Fruit weights were recorded, and the percentage weight loss from harvest was
151 calculated after 3 days of storage at 0 °C.
152 The volume of fluid sap supernatant of pre-stored, untreated and CO_2 -treated fruit was
153 calculated following centrifugation (Welbaum and Meinzer, 1990) at 350 or 2,000 x g
154 for 10 min after thawing frozen pieces of strawberries (2.2 g) at 25 °C. Once this
155 intercellular fluid was removed from the intercellular spaces by centrifugation, tissues
156 were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for further analysis of
157 microstructure, using low temperature scanning electron microscopy (LT-SEM). With this
158 technique sample components, including water are physically stabilized by freezing *in*
159 *situ*. Our LT-SEM studies are prepared as previously described (Goñi et al., 2011), using a
160 Zeiss DSN-960 electron scanning microscope equipped with a cold stage (Cryostrans
161 CT-1500, Oxford Instruments). Frozen tissue sections were cryofractured at -180 °C,
162 etched at -90 °C, gold-coated and subsequently transferred to the microscope where they
163 were analysed out at -150 to -160 °C. Samples were observed with both secondary and
164 retro-dispersed electrons, and the best images were selected in each case.

165 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

166 One-way ANOVA and correlational analyses were performed using SPSS ver. 19.0.
167 The multicomparison of means was assessed by Bonferroni's test, to determine the level
168 of significance at $P < 0.05$. The main effects of CO₂ treatment, storage time, and x
169 treatment time interaction on strawberry fruit were analyzed.

170

171 **3. Results and discussion**

172 **3.1. Effect of high CO₂ treatments on organic solute content**

173 We analyzed the profile of organic acids and free amino acids in wild strawberries cv.
174 Mara de Bois. Upon harvesting, citric acid was the most abundant organic acid ($10.68 \pm$
175 0.34 mg/g FW), followed by malic acid (4.97 ± 0.34 mg/g FW) (Fig. 1). Succinic acid
176 was detected at 0.56 ± 0.03 mg/g FW and oxalic acid 0.41 ± 0.09 mg/g FW. When
177 compared with freshly harvested fruit, significant increases in the concentration of both
178 oxalic and citric acid were only observed in fruit treated with 40% CO₂. Citrate
179 accumulation has been reported previously in cherimoya fruit stored in chilled
180 conditions (Alique et al., 1994) and in table grapes after prolonged storage at 2 °C
181 (Pretel et al., 2006). A significant increase in citrate was also reported in strawberries
182 exposed to high salinity (Keutgen and Pawelzik, 2008) and in bananas exposed to 60%
183 CO₂ at 20 °C (Liu et al., 2004) and under oxygen deprivation (Lara et al., 2011). Levels
184 of malic acid decreased significantly in strawberries treated with 20% CO₂, whereas in
185 untreated fruit and it that exposed to 40% CO₂ the levels of this metabolite did not differ
186 from those at the time of harvesting. In peel tissues of CO₂-treated fruit, malate levels
187 reported decreased, while they increase in air-treated fruit (Fernandez-Trujillo et al.,
188 2001). We previously reported a decrease in malic acid concentration when cherimoyas

189 were treated with CO₂, which is was closely linked to the increase in cytosolic NADP-
190 malic enzyme (Maldonado et al., 2004). Malic acid accumulation control could be related
191 with its important role in carbon metabolism and ionic homeostasis (Cheffings et al.,
192 1997). Based on the present findings, we propose that activation of malate metabolism is
193 associated with tolerance to short-term treatment with high CO₂ concentrations and
194 indeed, no such increase was observed in fruit treated with 40% CO₂. On the other
195 hand, the levels of succinic acid remained unchanged in fruit stored in air while a
196 marked increase in this acid was quantified in CO₂-treated fruit, mainly in fruit treated
197 with 20% CO₂. Succinate accumulation is a common response to CO₂ treatment in
198 many plant tissues (Ke et al., 1993), regardless of susceptibility to CO₂ injury,
199 suggesting that succinate accumulation may contribute to stress resistance rather than
200 inducing injury (Fernandez-Trujillo, 2001). We suggest that modifications in malic and
201 succinic acid should also be studied in the integrated metabolic processes of amino acid
202 biosynthesis via the GABA shunt and the anaplerotic pathway involving non-
203 photosynthetic CO₂ fixation, respectively. In this respect, although GABA represents a
204 very small fraction of the soluble amino acid pool at harvest, the highest levels of GABA
205 were observed in fruit treated with 40% CO₂. Indeed, GABA accumulation in response
206 to high CO₂ treatment has been reported previously in several fruit types (Merodio et
207 al., 1998; Ke et al., 1993), and this accumulation of GABA after prolonged storage at
208 low temperature in different cultivars of *Fragaria x ananassa* did not appear to be
209 consistently associated with fruit sensitivity to CO₂ (Deewatthanawong et al., 2010). It
210 remains unclear whether GABA is associated with stress or if it represents an adaptive
211 response of plant tissues. Moreover, the increase in GABA levels observed in 40% CO₂-
212 treated fruit was linked to a decline in glutamate levels (Table 1), suggesting that higher
213 levels of CO₂ increase the glutamate conversion to GABA via the GABA shunt pathway.

214 The production of GABA from glutamate that uses protons as cosubstrate has been
215 reported to be induced by decreasing intracellular pH (Crawford et al., 1994) and indeed,
216 higher acidification imposed by 40% CO₂ at 20°C has been reported (Lange and Kader,
217 1997). Not only GABA, but the highest levels of alanine were also quantified in 40% CO₂-
218 treated fruit. Alanine accumulation was confirmed during hypoxia induced by
219 waterlogging (Rocha et al., 2010) and under anoxia (Reggiani, 1988). The increase in
220 alanine content was concomitant with the greatest decline in aspartate in strawberries
221 treated with 40% CO₂ for 3 days. In contrast, proline levels increased significantly after
222 3 days of 20% CO₂ treatment while no differences were observed in 40% CO₂-treated
223 fruit, decreasing to undetectable levels in fruit stored in air as compared to freshly
224 harvested strawberries. Free proline has been reported to accumulate in a variety of
225 plants in response to a wide range of biotic and abiotic stressors. Several studies have
226 focused on the ability of proline to mediate osmotic adjustments, stabilize subcellular
227 structures and scavenge free radicals (Hare and Cress, 1997). Given the pool of free
228 proline in strawberries, the increase seen in response to 20% CO₂ is unlikely to have an
229 osmotic effect but rather, it may reflect a metabolic tolerance strategy, and so no such
230 accumulation was observed in 40% CO₂ treated fruit. We suggest that such metabolic
231 divergence in the accumulation of alanine, GABA, and proline between 20 and 40%
232 CO₂-treated strawberries may reflect the variation in the degree of tolerance to high CO₂
233 levels, and could help to distinguish between beneficial and stressful high CO₂
234 treatment. The levels of other amino acids, including serine, the predominant amino
235 acid in Mara de Bois strawberries ($5.470 \pm 0.13 \mu\text{mol/g FW}$) at harvest, CO₂ treatment
236 had minimal or no effect.

237 Changes in total soluble sugar content based on the sum of glucose, fructose and
238 sucrose are shown in Fig. 2. The highest levels of total sugars were detected in fruit

239 treated with 20% CO₂, with a weaker effect observed in that treated with 40% CO₂ and
240 no changes in fruit stored in air at 0 °C. Increased foliar carbohydrate levels have been
241 reported in plants exposed to CO₂ enriched versus CO₂ normal conditions (Hrubec et al.,
242 1985). The changes observed in total solute levels between untreated and CO₂-treated
243 fruit may be primarily attributed to a reduced carbohydrate demand for respiration.
244 Indeed, it has been proposed that the higher levels of carbohydrates observed in
245 controlled atmosphere storage conditions and following exposure to high levels of CO₂
246 can be attributed to a reduced rate of respiration (Kader, 2002; Ezz et al., 2004).

247

248 **3.2. Effect of CO₂ treatments on ion homeostasis**

249 Untreated fruit stored in air exhibited the lowest Na⁺ values while the highest levels
250 were detected in fruit treated with 40% CO₂ (Table 2). By contrast, the K⁺ concentration
251 was significantly lower in the 40% CO₂-treated versus untreated strawberries. As no
252 differences in Na⁺ or K⁺ were observed between strawberries treated with 20% CO₂ and
253 freshly harvested fruit, we reasoned that the degree of tolerance to high CO₂ (20%) was
254 sufficient to prevent alterations in ion homeostasis, although the underlying mechanism
255 remains unclear. Several stressors significantly decrease K⁺ concentrations in plants
256 (You et al., 2011) and mitigation of K⁺ loss is strongly correlated with salt tolerance
257 (Shabala and Cuin, 2007). Indeed, Orsini et al., (2011) confirmed the importance of
258 inorganic ions for osmotic adjustment under high salinity conditions. Based on our data,
259 we propose that rather than the absolute quantity of Na⁺ and K⁺ *per se*, the cytosolic
260 K⁺/Na⁺ ratio better reflects tolerance/damage to high levels of CO₂. Our results suggest
261 that treatment with 20% CO₂ maintains a K⁺/Na⁺ ratio similar to that found in freshly
262 harvested fruit, whereas a significant decrease in this ratio was provoked when fruit is
263 treated with 40% CO₂. Low temperature in the absence of CO₂ treatment also appears to

264 affect the relationship between these ions. Thus, untreated fruit stored in air at 0°C
265 exhibited the highest K⁺/Na⁺ ratio. With regard to divalent cations, tissues from 20%
266 CO₂-treated fruit showed significantly lower levels of Ca²⁺ compared with freshly
267 harvested fruit, however no differences were found in the case of Mg²⁺ levels (Table 2).
268 Cation levels play an important role in cross-linking with cell-wall polysaccharides and
269 by extension, in determining fruit tissue integrity (Tieman and Handa, 1994; Jarvis,
270 1982). The reduction in free soluble Ca²⁺ observed in 20% CO₂-treated fruit may
271 indicate greater stabilization of the cell wall. By contrast, the significant increase in free
272 soluble Ca²⁺ detected in 40% CO₂-treated fruit, possibly due to the dissolution of
273 calcium pectate and the consequent migration of calcium to the water-soluble fraction,
274 may result in increased cell wall swelling and porosity, and alterations in turgor.

275 **3.4. Water loss, distribution and microstructural characteristics of untreated and** 276 **CO₂-treated wild strawberry tissues.**

277 As in shown in Fig. 3A, while untreated fruit stored in air lost weight markedly after 3
278 days of storage at 0 °C, CO₂ treatment attenuated this weight loss, indicating that overall
279 water loss due mainly to transpiration was less in CO₂-treated fruit. Indeed, the lowest
280 values of water loss were observed in fruit treated with 40% CO₂ for 3 days. To
281 examine the water distribution in response to high CO₂ concentrations, the volume of
282 the fluid recovered was carried out following centrifugation (Fig. 3B) and further
283 illustrated using LT-SEM. The fluid volume in tissues of pre-stored fruit (day 0) was
284 189.77 μl/g FW and this value increased significantly in untreated fruit stored in air for
285 3 days to 257.95 μl/g FW (+ 135%). Exposure to 20% CO₂ for 3 days had no effect on
286 the volume recovered (Fig. 3B), whereas 40% CO₂ induced the sharp increase with
287 respect to pre-stored tissues (+144 %). As the equivalent centrifugation values to those
288 used here previously resulted in retention at the surface of substantial volumes of sugar

289 solution in pockets of the cut cells due to surface tension (Dong et al., 1994), we therefore
290 carried out additional studies using higher centrifugations. The fluid recovery values
291 were clearly reinforced by the microstructural data (Fig. 4 and 5), showing the
292 differences in the juice leakage, amount of space between cells and providing a more
293 complete description of the strawberry cell structure. In fresh strawberry (Fig. 4),
294 epidermis (Fig. 4a) consists of a single cell layer fitting closely together, where the
295 achenes (real one-seeded fruit) are embedded (Fig. 4b) and covered with special wall
296 layers on their outer (cuticle and wax, Fig. 4c). The strawberry receptacle cortical
297 parenchyma cells (Fig. 4c) are irregular small cells, which are different in shape and
298 volume from those of the flesh located in the interior of receptacle tissue. The vertical
299 middle section of the parenchyma is made up of higher cells (between 110-160 μm) (Fig.
300 4d). Microstructural characteristics of parenchymal cells (1.7-2 mm deep) in untreated and
301 CO_2 -treated wild strawberry tissue is shown in Figure 5. Images showing the differences
302 between freshly harvested (Fig. 5A), untreated (Fig. 5B), 20% CO_2 (Fig. 5C) and 40%
303 CO_2) treated tissue (Fig. 5D) after centrifugation were compared with the corresponding
304 non-centrifuged tissues (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5c and 5d). The most striking feature of the untreated
305 fruit stored in air (Fig. 5b) is the layer of cell sap covering the cells, which was also
306 evident in fruit treated with 40% CO_2 (Fig. 5d). Furthermore, in the latter cells the
307 intercellular spaces were inundated with aqueous solution, effectively reducing the void
308 volume. The fluid in the spaces was not just water, but a solution of ionic compounds was
309 detected (data not shown). The image of the fluid in the spaces is similar with the image of
310 intracellular content (Fig. 5d). Using NMR microscopy, strawberry parenchyma tissues
311 infected with *Botrytis cinerea* was shown to have much longer T_2 values than healthy
312 tissues, due to the inundation of intercellular gas spaces with intracellular fluid released
313 following cell wall damage (Goodman et al., 1996). Strawberries treated with 20% CO_2

314 (Fig. 5c) exhibited less fluid sap and large, empty intercellular spaces. Air-filled
315 intercellular spaces are necessary and ubiquitous in higher plants (Woolley, 1983). As
316 such, the excess of aqueous solution found in the tissues of untreated and 40% CO₂-
317 treated fruit may have deleterious effects, possibly by blocking gas diffusion. With
318 regard to the centrifugated tissue microstructural analyses, only the cells of 20% CO₂-
319 treated fruit (Fig. 5C) and those of pre-stored fruit (Fig. 5A) were found to retain to a
320 greater extent their cell shape and integrity. The larger volume of fluid observed in the
321 intercellular spaces in fruit treated with 40% CO₂ (Fig. 5D) and in untreated fruit stored
322 in air (Fig. 5B) suggests changes in the mechanical properties of the cell wall,
323 membrane permeability and tissue water status. Furthermore, the differences in water
324 distribution and microstructural changes in strawberries could be responsible for the
325 lack of understanding of the alterations in softening caused by stressful storage
326 conditions. With regard to foregoing, our unpublished results show a marked decrease
327 in the unfreezable water fraction, which corresponds to strongly bound water, in 40%
328 CO₂-treated fruit, concomitant with an increase in total water potential and a marked
329 decrease in protective compounds such as FOS which exhibited a high water binding
330 capacity.

331 Therefore, we conclude that beneficial short-term treatment with 20% CO₂, as opposed
332 to both 40% CO₂ and untreated fruit stored in air, led to an increase in cellular water
333 retention that was associated with an accumulation of osmolytes, some of which exerted
334 cell protection and regulated ion homeostasis, in addition to mediating osmotic
335 adjustments. Furthermore, given the divergent patterns observed in the levels of several
336 metabolites in fruit treated with 20% or 40% CO₂, including proline and malic acid, we
337 propose that the corresponding metabolic pathways play a regulatory role in CO₂
338 tolerance. Further studies will be necessary to determine whether water reabsorption

339 from the intercellular spaces occurs after transfer of CO₂-treated fruit to air, and to
340 identify the mechanisms underlying the increase in the protective agents in the tissues of
341 20% CO₂-treated fruit.

342

343 **Acknowledgements**

344 This work was supported by CICYT Project AGL2008-02949. M. Blanch was
345 supported by a postdoctoral fellowship from the CSIC (Spain). The authors thank Estela
346 Vega and Gonzalo Guerrero for their helpful support.

347

348 **References**

349 Alique, R., Zamorano, J.P., Calvo, M.L., Merodio, C., De la Plaza, J.L., 1994. Tolerance
350 of cherimoya (*Annona cherimola* Mill.) to cold storage. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.* 119,
351 524-528.

352 Almenar, E., Hernandez-Munoz, P., Lagaron, J.M., Catala, R., Gavara, R., 2006.
353 Controlled atmosphere storage of wild strawberry fruit (*Fragaria vesca* L.). *J. Agric.*
354 *Food Chem.* 54, 86-91.

355 Blanch, M., Sanchez-Ballesta, M.T., Escribano, M.I., Merodio, C., 2011. Fructo-
356 oligosaccharides in table grapes and response to storage. *Food Chem.* 129, 724–730.

357 Bodelón, O.G., Blanch, M., Sanchez-Ballesta, M.T., Escribano, M.I., Merodio, C. 2010.
358 The effects of high CO₂ levels on anthocyanin composition, antioxidant activity and
359 soluble sugar content of strawberries stored at low non-freezing temperature. *Food*
360 *Chem.* 122 (3), 673-678.

361 Bouche, N., Fromm, H., 2004. GABA in plants: just a metabolite? *Trends Plant Sci.* 9,
362 110–115.

363 Cataldi, T.R., Margiotta, G., Del Fiore, A., Bufo, S.A., 2003. Ionic content in plant
364 extracts determined by ion chromatography with conductivity detection. *Phytochem.*
365 *Anal.* 14 (3), 176-83.

366 Crawford, L.A., Bown, A.W., Breitzkreuz, K.E., Guinel F.C. 1994. The synthesis of γ -
367 aminobutyric acid in response to treatments reducing cytosolic pH. *Plant Physiol.*
368 104:865-871.

369 Cheffings, C.M., Pantoja, O., Ashcroft, F.M., Smith, J.A.C. 1997. Malate transport and
370 vacuolar ion channels in CAM plants. *J. Exp. Bot.* 48, 623-631.

371 Deewatthanawong, R., Nock, J.F., Watkins, C.B., 2010. γ -Aminobutyric acid (GABA)
372 accumulation in four strawberry cultivars in response to elevated CO₂ storage.
373 *Postharvest Biol. Technol.* 57, 92-96.

374 Dong, Z., Canny, M.J., McCully, M.E., Roboredo, M.R., Cabadilla, C.F., Ortega, E.,
375 Rodés, R., 1994. A nitrogen-fixing endophyte of sugarcane stems (A new role for
376 the apoplast). *Plant Physiol.* 105, 1139-1147.

377 Ezz, T.M., Ritenour, M.A., Brecht, J.K., 2004. Hot water and elevated CO₂ effects on
378 proline and other compositional changes in relation to postharvest chilling injury of
379 ‘Marsh’ Grapefruit. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.* 129 (4), 576-582.

380 Fernández-Trujillo, J.P., Nock, J.F., Watkins, C.B., 1999. Fermentative metabolism and
381 organic acid concentrations of strawberry fruit cultivars with different tolerances to
382 carbon dioxide. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.* 124, 696–701.

383 Fernández-Trujillo, J.P., Nock, J.F., Watkins, C.B., 2001. Superficial scald, carbon
384 dioxide injury, and changes of fermentation products and organic acids in ‘Cortland’

385 and 'Law Rome' apples after high carbon dioxide stress treatment. J. Amer. Soc.
386 Hort. Sci. 126(2), 235-241.

387 Goodman, B.A., Williamson, B., Simpson, E.J., Chudek, J.A., Hunter, G., Prior,
388 D.A.M. 1996. High field NMR microscopic imaging of cultivated strawberry fruit.
389 Magn. Reson. Imaging. 14, 187-96.

390 Goñi, O., Fernandez-Caballero, C., Sanchez-Ballesta, M.T., Escribano, M.I., Merodio,
391 C., 2011. Water status and quality improvement in high-CO₂ treated table grapes
392 Food. 128 (1), 34-39.

393 Hare, P.D., Cress, W.A., 1997. Metabolic implications of stress-induced proline
394 accumulation in plants. Plant Growth Regul. 21, 79-102.

395 Hitmi, A., Coudret, A., Barthomeuf, C., Sallanon, H. 2000. Role of intracellular water
396 retention strength in freezing tolerance of *Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium* Vis.
397 cell cultures. J. Plant Physiol. 157, 47-53.

398 Hrubec, T.C., Robinson, J.M., Robert, P.D., 1985. Effects of CO₂ enrichment and
399 carbohydrate content on the dark respiration of soybeans. Plant Physiol. 79,684-689.

400 Jarvis, M.C., 1982. The proportion of calcium-bound pectin in plant cell walls. Planta.
401 154, 344-346.

402 Kader, A.A., 2002. Postharvest technology of horticultural crops. University of
403 California, Division of Agriculture and Natural Resources Publication 3311. pag
404 535.

405 Ke, D., Goldstein, L., O'Mahony, M., Kader, A.A., 1991. Effects of short-term exposure
406 to low O₂ and high CO₂ atmospheres on quality attributes of strawberries. J.Food
407 Sci. 56(1): 50-54.

408 Ke, D., Mateos, M., Siriphanich, J., Li, C., Kader, A.A., 1993. Carbon dioxide action on
409 metabolism of organic and amino acids in crisphead lettuce. *Postharvest Biol.*
410 *Technol.* 3, 235-247.

411 Keutgen, A.J., Pawelzik, E., 2008. Quality and nutritional value of strawberry fruit
412 under long term salt stress. *Food Chem.* 107 (4), 1413-1420.

413 Kinnersley, AM., Turano, F.J., 2000. Gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA) and plant
414 responses to stress. *CRC Crit. Rev. Plant Sci.* 19, 479-509.

415 Lara, M.V., Budde, C.O., Porrini, L., Borsani, J., Murray, R., Andreo, C.S., Drincovich,
416 M.F. 2011. Peach (*Prunus Persica*) fruit response to anoxia: reversible ripening
417 delay and biochemical changes. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 52, 392-403.

418 Lange, D.L., Kader, A.A., 1997. Elevated carbon dioxide exposure alters intracellular pH
419 and energy charge in avocado fruit tissue. *J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci.* 122 (2) 253-257.

420 Liu, S., Yang, Y., Murayama, H., Taira, S., Fukushima, T., 2004. Effects of CO₂ on
421 respiratory metabolism in ripening banana fruit. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.* 33, (1),
422 27-34

423 Maldonado, R., Sanchez-Ballesta, M.T., Alique, R., Escribano, M.I., Merodio, C.,
424 2004. Malate metabolism and adaptation to chilling temperature storage by
425 pretreatment with high CO₂ levels in *Annona cherimola* Fruit. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*
426 52 (15), 4758-4763.

427 Menegus, F., Cattaruzza, L., Chersi, A., Fronza, G. 1989. Differences in the anaerobic
428 lactate-succinate production and in the changes of cell sap pH for plants with high
429 and low resistance to anoxia. *Plant Physiol.* 90, 29-32.

430 Merodio, C., Muñoz, M.T., Cura, B., del Buitrago, D., Escribano, M.I., 1998. Effect of
431 high CO₂ level on the titres of gamma-aminobutyric acid, total polyamines and
432 some pathogenesis-related proteins in cherimoya fruit stored at low temperature. J.
433 Exp. Bot. 49, 1339-1347.

434 Muñoz, T., Ruiz-Cabello, J., Molina-García, A., Escribano, M.I., Merodio, C., 2001.
435 Chilling temperature storage changes the inorganic phosphate pool distribution in
436 cherimoya (*Annona cherimola*) fruit. J. Amer. Soc. Hort. Sci. 126, 122-127.

437 Orsini, F., Accorsi, M., Gianquinto, G., Dinelli, G., Antognoni, F., Ruiz Carrasco, K.,
438 Martinez, E.A., Alnayef, M., Marotti, I., Bosi, S., Biondi, S. 2011. Beyond the ionic
439 and osmotic response to salinity in *Chenopodium quinoa*: functional elements of
440 successful halophytism. *Funct. Plant Biol.* 38, 818-831.

441 Ponce-Valadez, M., Watkins, C.B., 2008. Fermentation and malate metabolism in
442 response to elevated CO₂ concentrations in two strawberry cultivars. *Physiol. Plant.*
443 134(1), 121-33.

444 Pretel, M.T., Martínez-Madrid, M.C., Martínez, J.R., Carreño, J.C., Romojaro, F., 2006.
445 Prolonged storage of 'Aledo' table grapes in a slightly CO₂ enriched atmosphere in
446 combination with generators of SO₂. *LWT-Food Sci. Technol.* 39(10), 1109-1116.

447 Reggiani, R., Cantu, A.C., Brambilla, I., Bertani, A., 1988. Accumulation and
448 Interconversion of Amino Acids in Rice Roots under Anoxia. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 29,
449 981-987.

450 Roberts, J.K.M., Hooks, M.A., Miaullis, A.P., Edwards, S., Webster, C., 1992.
451 Contribution of malate and amino acid metabolism to cytoplasmic pH regulation in
452 hypoxic maize root tips studied using nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy.
453 *Plant Physiol.* 98: 480-487.

454 Rocha, M., Licausi, F., Araújo, W.L., Nunes-Nesi, A., Sodek, L., Fernie, A.R., Van
455 Dongen, J.T., 2010. Glycolysis and the tricarboxylic acid cycle are linked by alanine
456 aminotransferase during hypoxia induced by waterlogging of *Lotus japonicus*. *Plant*
457 *Physiol.* 152, 1501-1513.

458 Shabala, S., Cuin, T.A., 2007. Potassium transport and plant salt tolerance. *Physiol.*
459 *Plantarum.* 133, 651-669.

460 Tieman, D.M., Handa, A.K., 1994. Reduction in pectin methylesterase activity modifies
461 tissue integrity and cation levels in ripening tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill)
462 fruits. *Plant Physiol.* 106, 429-436.

463 Valluru, R., Van den Ende, W. 2008. Plant fructans in stress environments: emerging
464 concepts and future prospects. *J. Exp. Bot.* 59, 2905-2916.

465 Vertucci, C.W., Stushnuff, C., 1992. The state of water in acclimating vegetative buds
466 form *Malus* and *Amelanchier* and its relationship to winter hardiness. *Physiol.*
467 *Plantarum.* 86, 503-511.

468 Welbaum, G.E., Meinzer, F.C., 1990. Compartmentation of solutes and water in
469 developing sugarcane stalk tissue. *Plant Physiol.* 93, 1147-53.

470 Woolley, J.T., 1983. Maintenance of air in intercellular spaces of plants. *Plant Physiol.*
471 72, 989-991.

472 Yoshida, S., 1994. Low temperature-induced cytoplasmic acidosis in cultured mung
473 bean (*Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek) cells. *Plant Physiol.* 104:1131-1138.

474 You, M.P., Colmer, T.D., Barbetti, M.J. 2011. Salinity drives host reaction in *Phaseolus*
475 *vulgaris* (common bean) to *Macrophomina phaseolina*. *Funct. Plant Biol.* 38, 984-
476 992.

477

478

479 **Figure captions**

480 **Figure 1.** Oxalic, citric, succinic and malic acid content in *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara
481 de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0
482 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. The data are presented as the mean ± SE of
483 three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant differences ($P<0.05$).

484

485 **Figure 2.** Total soluble sugar content (glucose, fructose and sucrose) in *Fragaria x*
486 *vesca* cv. Mara de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3
487 days of storage at 0 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. The data are presented
488 as the mean ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant differences
489 ($P<0.05$).

490

491 **Figure 3.** Weight loss (%) and fluid recovery (μL/g FW) in *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara
492 de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0
493 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. The data are presented as the mean ± SE of
494 three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant differences ($P<0.05$).

495

496 **Figure 4.** LT-SEM micrographs showing the layer of cells of freshly harvested
497 strawberries *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois. (a) Fresh strawberry showing single
498 layer of rectangular epidermal cells (1). (b) Image showing the distribution of achenes
499 (2). (c) Strawberry receptacle cortical parenchyma region with irregular cells. (d)
500 Strawberry receptacle cortical parenchyma region with large cells.

501

502 **Figure 5.** Microstructural analysis of parenchymal cells of *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara
503 de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0

504 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. Each photograph shows a cross-fractured
505 face of one cell in the center. Small letters (a, b, c and d) correspond to the samples
506 before centrifugation while the capital letters (A, B, C and D) indicate samples after
507 centrifugation. Scale bars represent 50 μm.

508

Referees

- Christopher Brian, Watkins. Roberts Hall, Room 356. Department of Horticulture, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY 14853, United States. cbw3@cornell.edu
- Juan Pablo Fernández-Trujillo. Professor and Secretary of the Agronomical Engineering School (UPCT). Department of Agricultural and Food Engineering, Technical University of Cartagena (UPCT), Campus Paseo Alfonso XIII, 48, ETSIA and Institute of Plant Biotechnology, E-30203 Cartagena (Murcia), Spain. j68es@terra.es / juanp.fdez@upct.es
- Carlos Vicente Córdoba. Department of Plant Physiology, Faculty of Biology, Complutense University, Madrid, Spain. cvicente@bio.ucm.es

Table

Table 1: Changes on the content of free amino acids (FAAs) in strawberry *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois pre-stored, untreated and 20% CO₂ or 40%CO₂-treated stored for 3 days at 0 °C, calculated in μmol/g FW .

	pre-stored	untreated	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
Gaba	0.027±0.00 ^a	0.057±0.01 ^b	0.058±0.01 ^b	0.150±0.01 ^c
Gln	1.451±0.07 ^a	1.570±0.34 ^a	1.760±0.26 ^a	1.354±0.13 ^a
Pro	0.006±0.01 ^a	N.D.	0.039±0.01 ^b	0.006±0.01 ^a
Asp	0.746±0.03 ^b	0.711±0.17 ^b	0.563±0.06 ^{ab}	0.439±0.03 ^a
Thr	0.259±0.02 ^a	0.244±0.06 ^a	0.278±0.03 ^a	0.216±0.02 ^a
Ser	5.470±0.13 ^a	6.089±1.43 ^a	5.835±0.69 ^a	5.068±0.29 ^a
Glu	0.611±0.03 ^b	0.63±0.15 ^b	0.937±0.09 ^c	0.212±0.03 ^a
Gly	0.143±0.01 ^a	0.131±0.03 ^a	0.185±0.02 ^a	0.173±0.02 ^a
Ala	0.859±0.03 ^a	0.813±0.19 ^a	1.284±0.15 ^b	1.395±0.10 ^b
Cys	0.040±0.00 ^a	0.038±0.00 ^a	0.038±0.01 ^a	0.038±0.00 ^a
Val	0.159±0.01 ^a	0.156±0.02 ^a	0.173±0.00 ^a	0.162±0.00 ^a
Met	0.072±0.00 ^a	0.052±0.01 ^b	0.047±0.00 ^b	0.038±0.00 ^b
Ile	0.044±0.00 ^a	0.038±0.01 ^a	0.047±0.00 ^a	0.043±0.00 ^a
Leu	0.050±0.00 ^b	0.022±0.02 ^a	0.038±0.01 ^{ab}	0.039±0.00 ^{ab}
Tyr	0.016±0.00 ^a	0.011±0.01 ^a	0.022±0.00 ^a	0.020±0.00 ^a
Phe	0.045±0.00 ^a	0.035±0.01 ^a	0.043±0.00 ^a	0.037±0.00 ^a
His	0.029±0.00 ^a	0.026±0.01 ^a	0.021±0.02 ^a	N.D.
Lys	0.001±0.00 ^a	0.008±0.00 ^b	0.014±0.00 ^{bc}	0.020±0.00 ^c
Arg	0.024±0.01 ^{ab}	0.013±0.01 ^a	0.032±0.00 ^b	0.039±0.01 ^b

The data are presented as the means ±SE of the three replicates (n=6) and the different letters indicate significant differences ($P<0.05$).

Table 2: Changes of the content of total soluble ions of strawberry *Fragaria x vesca* cv. Mara de Bois pre-stored, untreated and 20%CO₂ or 40%CO₂-treated stored for 3 days at 0 °C. Data are expressed per 100g of fresh weight (Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺).

	pre-stored	untreated	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
<i>MONOVALENT</i>				
Na⁺[mg]	2.89±0.39 ^b	2.26±0.20 ^a	2.73±0.12 ^b	3.95±0.17 ^c
K⁺ [mg]	168.90±3.61 ^{ab}	176.18±1.83 ^a	171.39±6.34 ^{ab}	160.66±11.30 ^b
K⁺/Na⁺[relative units]	59.22±8.41 ^b	78.19±6.50 ^c	62.83±4.04 ^b	40.72±3.17 ^a
<i>DIVALENT</i>				
Ca²⁺[mg]	11.01±0.26 ^b	10.81±0.32 ^b	9.47±0.27 ^a	11.93±0.27 ^c
Mg²⁺[mg]	12.41±0.15 ^a	13.42±0.46 ^b	12.74±0.54 ^{ac}	13.31±0.15 ^{bc}

The data are presented as the means ±SE of the three replicates (n=6) and the different letters within rows indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$

Figure

□ pre-stored □ air □ 20%CO₂ ■ 40%CO₂

Figure

Figure

Figure

Figure

pre-stored

3d air

3d 20%CO₂

3d 40%CO₂